

Anexo 2: Research Instrument

Questionnaire to measure the variable Energy drinks consumption

Dear Participant:

This research is being conducted by students of César Vallejo University. The data collected will be anonymous, treated confidentially, and used solely for academic purposes. Therefore, I voluntarily consent to participate in the research entitled "Energy drinks consumption and sleeping quality of students' universities of the Chiclayo province, Peru" by answering YES () or NO ().

I also authorize the publication of the results of this research while maintaining my anonymity.

Mark with an 'X' evaluating each item or statement according to the scale:

Strongly agree (SA)	In agreement (A)	Neither agree nor disagree (N)	Disagree (D)	Strongly Disagree (TD)
5	4	3	2	1

	SA	A	N	D	TD
Dimension 1: Consumption	5	4	3	2	1
I frequently consume energy drinks.					
I drink several bottles or cans of energy drinks in a single day.					
I consume energy drinks regularly.					
I consume energy drinks at specific times, such as at night or in the early morning.					
I have consumed energy drinks for several months or years.					
Dimension 2: Motives					
I consume energy drinks to increase my energy level.					

I consume energy drinks to improve my concentration level.					
I consume energy drinks to improve my academic or work performance.					
I consume energy drinks when I participate in meetings or with friends.					
I consume energy drinks in stressful situations.					
Dimension 3: <i>Perceived effects</i>					
I feel nervous after consuming energy drinks.					
I have experienced palpitations after consuming energy drinks.					
I feel more tired after the initial effect of energy drinks wears off.					
I have difficulty sleeping after consuming energy drinks.					
I feel irritable or moody after consuming energy drinks.					

Thank you very much for your participation!

Questionnaire to measure the variable Sleeping Quality

Dear Participant:

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I also authorize the publication of the results of this research while maintaining my anonymity.

Mark with an 'X' evaluating each item or statement according to the scale:

Strongly agree (SA)	Agree (A)	Neither agree or disagree (N)	Disagree (D)	Strongly Disagree (TD)
5	4	3	2	1

	SA	A	N	D	TD
Dimension 1: Sleep duration	5	4	3	2	1
I sleep less than 7 hours a night.					
I usually rest at a specific time every day.					
My sleep usually remains continuous throughout the night without interruptions.					
How often do I wake up during the night for unintentional reasons (such as thirst, heat, or noise).					
I need to take naps because I don't sleep well at night.					
Dimension 2: Sleep efficiency					
I have trouble falling asleep when I go to bed.					
How often do external or emotional factors (such as noise or thoughts) interrupt my sleep.					

My sleep is shallow and not restorative.					
When I wake up I still feel tired or without energy.					
I feel that, even though I sleep the usual number of hours, I don't recover.					
Dimension 3: <i>Daytime consequences</i>					
I feel drowsy or sleepy during the day.					
I have difficulty concentrating due to lack of sleep.					
I feel irritable or moody because I sleep poorly.					
When I wake up I still feel tired or without energy.					
My academic performance is affected by my poor sleep.					

Thank you very much for your participation!